

SECTION: VALUES AND INNOVATION

ETHNIC DIVERSITY, VALUES DIVERSITY AND INNOVATION: A CROSS-COUNTRY ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: The contribution of innovation to economic growth and development and the “hard” antecedents of innovation performance are well known. What is less known is the impact of the “soft” factors, in particular, socio-cultural forces on the patterns of technological innovation. In this study we evaluate the effects of various types of cultural diversities - ethnic, religious, language and values - on innovation performance of a country. We use well-known measures of ethnic, religious and linguistic diversity within a country as well as a purpose-built values diversity measure to evaluate the impact of innovation performance. Using a sample of 61 countries, we find that cultural diversities influence the inputs of innovation. Greater ethnic diversity within a country has a negative impact on innovation performance while values diversity has a positive effect. Our findings have important policy implications, particularly on immigration policies.

JEL CLASSIFICATIONS: O30, Z10

KEYWORDS: Ethnic diversity, values diversity, innovation, creativity

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1. Introduction

Recent events worldwide have put diversity in the limelight. The decision of the US Supreme Court to allow same-sex marriage throughout the country, the race-hate crimes in several states of the US, religious hate-crimes in Myanmar, Syria and Nigeria and continuous illegal immigration into Europe and Australia have dominated the international news media in recent years. At the workplace, the lack of diversity has also been highlighted. Various media reports tend to show that major companies in the US are not very diverse. For example, as of 2016, only 4 percent of Facebook’s US employees are Hispanic and 2 percent are black (www.theinstitute.ieee.org) while at Google its 3 percent and 2 percent respectively (www.execed.economist.com).

The benefits of a diverse workplace include better decision-making, improved problem solving, greater creativity and innovation, enhanced product development and successful marketing to a wide range of customers (Cox, 1991; Harvey & Allard, 2012). A recent study of 366 companies by McKinsey (Hunt et al., 2014) found that companies that rank high in gender diversity were 15% more likely to have better financial performance than the

national industry median. For companies with high ethnic diversity within the senior management level, they were 30% more likely to outperform the national industry median. Diversity can also be detrimental to an organization as efforts to assimilate a diverse workforce into a cohesive group may lead to a decrease in productivity at the initial stage or if such efforts fail (Fine, 1996). In a natural field experiment conducted at a flower packaging plant in Kenya, Hjort (2014) found that plant productivity could have increased by 4-8% if segregation of antagonistic ethnic groups was allowed. Such inconclusive results led Alesina & Ferrara (2005) to conclude that “while in poor economies ethnic diversity may not be beneficial from the point of view of productivity, it may be so in rich ones ... (because) variety in skills are more likely to be relevant for more advanced societies” (p. 770).

The positive effects of innovation on economic performance is well established (Freeman, 1990). Likewise, the importance of the various links that makes up the national innovation system has also been studied (Bartels, Voss, Lederer, S., & Bachtrog, 2012). In addition, since Shane (1993), there has been a steady growth in studies that links culture and innovation (Efrat, 2014; Taylor & Wilson, 2012; Rauch, Frese, Wang, Unger, Lozada et al., 2013). In these studies however, national culture is assumed to be homogenous within the country. In other words, a country is said to be high or low in power distance or individualistic or collectivist in nature. The diversity in culture that exists within the country has not been addressed. Since globalization allows for the freer movement of people and ideas across borders, the assumption of homogeneity of beliefs, attitudes and behavior within a nation-state is weak.

In this paper, we evaluate the effects of two main types of diversity on the innovation performance of a nation. First, we consider the effect of outward diversity, namely ethnic, religious and linguistic diversities. We ask if such outward diversities do indeed contribute towards creativity and innovation, or whether these diversities lead to greater conflicts that harm innovative efforts. Second, we consider the effect of values diversity on innovation output. Values are those inner principles that influence one’s outer attitude and behavior. Thus, diversity in values may reflect those inner differences that transcend the color of the skin and language. A nation may consist of either or both type of diversities, thus, we also consider the joint effect of these diversities on innovation. We find that ethnic diversity has a negative effect on innovation while other types of diversities, particularly values diversity, positively contribute to innovation. In both cases however, the effect is mainly indirect, in that diversity influences the determinants of innovation.

In the next section, we develop several hypotheses based on existing literature on diversity and innovation. In section 3, we explain the measurements of diversity, in particular values diversity, a measure that has been developed specifically for this study. In section 4, the methodology of our analysis is explained followed by our results. In section 5 we discuss our findings and conclude.

2. Culture, diversity and innovation

The determinants of innovation at a macro level is well explained by the much cited work of Furman et al. (2002) who uses a framework that combines Romer’s growth model, Porter’s model of national competitive advantage (Porter’s diamond) and works relating to the

national innovation systems, to show key factors that influences international patent registrations. The framework highlights three key components that contribute towards greater innovation: the presence of a strong innovation infrastructure which includes science and technology policy environment, mechanisms to support basic research, higher education, and the stock of technological knowledge; a supportive microeconomic environment that supports industrial clusters; and the strength of the linkages between the innovation infrastructure and the specific clusters, in particular, the link between universities and industries. While Furman et al.'s (2002) framework explains the "hard" factors contributing towards innovation; it ignores "soft" components like culture.

Culture as an instrumental variable that influences innovation, both at the firm and national levels is quite established. At the firm level, a meta-analytic study by Rosenbusch, Brinckmann, & Bausch (2011) confirmed that the innovation-performance relationship is moderated by third variables including culture, while at the cross-country level, Lubart (1999) and Baumol (2002) for instance, have included traditions and culture embedded within a society in their theories on creativity and innovation. Cultural orientations have been used to explain why Asians tend to be less creative than Westerners (Noriko, Fan, & Van Dusen, 2001) and why tight cultures can be detrimental to generating novel ideas (Chua, Roth, & Lemoine, 2015).

Extending this line of study, numerous studies have also considered specific cultural orientation to innovation. Hofstede's various dimensions of culture have been popular in this regard (Kumar, 2014). Shane (1993) found that individualistic societies with high levels of uncertainty avoidance but low power distance are the best innovators. Looking at European countries in particular, Hussler (2004) found that high uncertainty avoidance and high power distance countries are better imitators than innovators. Taylor & Wilson (2012) confirm that individualism does promote innovation but some aspects of collectivism (nationalism and patriotism) can have similar effects as well. By considering the national cultural orientation and the personal values orientation of individual entrepreneurs simultaneously, Rauch et al. (2013) show why there might be inconsistencies in specific cultural orientations and innovation performance. That innovation is more pronounce in cultures with low uncertainty avoidance and low power distance did not receive empirical support in their study of 5 diverse countries. Using 35 of the richest countries, Efrat (2014) conclude that while culture still matters for innovation, globalization activities are changing the impact of certain orientations. They find power distance to have lost its influence while low uncertainty avoidance seems to promote higher rates of innovation. It is clear from the brief review above that there is no consistency in previous findings that links a specific cultural orientation to innovation output. Results vary according to geography, time and levels of economic development, among other reasons.

Previous studies that considered national culture and innovation performance can be criticized for the assumption of cultural homogeneity within a given nation state. Tung (2008) explains that a reduction in the barriers to migration and cross-border movement of the work force has resulted in a more heterogeneous population within a country. In an earlier work, Au (1999) had alluded to intra-cultural variation and pointed to the fact that it is possible for two countries to be similar based on cultural means but with a large variance. More recently, Avloniti & Filippaios (2014) recognized the limitations of national averages to

measure cultural distance, while Venaik & Midgley (2015) identifies the existence of four archetypes of values within a society.

The heterogeneity within a nation has been addressed in economic literature as fractionalization (Alesina, Devleeschauwer, Easterly, Kurlat, & Wacziarg, 2003), ethnic or religious diversity (Montalvo & Reynal-Querol, 2003, 2005, 2005a) or generally cultural diversity (Ager & Bruckner, 2013). In a review article, Alesina & Ferrara (2005) explain that diversity leads to resource allocation policies which are unbalanced resulting in conflicts in preferences, racism and prejudices among the ethnic groups within a nation leading to political unrest. Diversity can result in individuals giving preference to or transacting exclusively with members of their own group. Such exclusivity can lead the group to penalize members who carry out acts outside the group norms (e.g. innovate) (Berman, 2000). However, diversity also leads to a combination of different abilities and experiences which encourages innovation and creativity. The positive effects of diversity include innovative ways in problem-solving (Hong & Page, 1998), by considering different perspective to arrive at an optimal solution. This tends to happen among more industrialized countries that have developed institutions and are better able to cope with such diversities. Studies that link diversity within a group to innovation and/or productivity tend to be at the organizational level (e.g. Jackson & Ruderman, 1996; Richard, Kochan, & McMillan-Capehart, 2002). Perhaps an indirect measure that has been attempted thus far at a country level, has been the link between immigration and economic growth. OECD (2014) for example, argue that migrants arrive with various skills and abilities and supplement the stock of human capital that already exist in the host country. There is evidence for this in the US (Hunt, 2010) but not in New Zealand (Mare, Fabling, & Stillman, 2011). In a recent study, Bove & Elia (2017) show that cultural heterogeneity has increased in recent years due to the dramatic increase in mass migration. By separating countries based on their initial level of development, they were able to show that an increase in diversity resulting from immigration is good for economic growth, particularly for developing countries. The effect of cultural diversity on innovation at the country level has not been tested.

Although firm level studies like Parrotta, Pozzoli, & Pytlikova (2014) show that a 10% change in ethnic diversity can increase the number of patent applications by about 2.2%, these tend to be only for white-collar occupations. Similar to Parrotta et al. (2014), studies like Ostergaard, Timmermans, & Kristinsson (2011), Sollner (2010) and Ozgen, Nijkamp, & Poot (2013) rely on firms in Europe. Even the McKinsey study (Hunt et al., 2014) that links ethnic diversity to firm performance relies on diversity at the top management level rather than across the firm. In contrast, studies that link diversity to economic growth tend to show a negative relationship (Easterly & Levine, 1997; Alesina et al., 2003, Montalvo & Reynal-Querol, 2005a). Goren (2014) also finds a direct negative relationship between ethnic diversity and real GDP per capita growth, but also point to the indirect channels through which ethnic diversity affects growth, namely schooling, political instability, market distortions, foreign trade and fertility rate. In like manner, we argue that at a national level, cultural diversity (ethnic, religious and linguistic) will have a negative impact on national innovation performance. Cultural diversity reduces the provision of public goods including investments in education and R&D, as the main focus will be on political and social stability. Thus, we hypothesize that:

H1a: *Ethnic diversity contributes negatively to national innovation performance*

H1b: *Religious diversity contributes negatively to national innovation performance*

H1c: *Linguistic diversity contributes negatively to national innovation performance*

However, diversity thus far has been limited to ethnic, religious and linguistic (ERL) groupings within a country. On the basis of ERL, a recent study by Goren (2013) concluded that countries in Sub-Saharan Africa are highly diverse whereas countries in Europe, particularly the Scandinavian nations, and Latin America, particularly Brazil and Argentina, are less. Literature tends to assume that individual values stems from ERL, and so accounting for these differences are sufficient to explain values differences. This is because of the assumption that “people agree within groups and disagree across groups, so that cultural (*generally defined as values, norms and attitudes*) heterogeneity and ethnic heterogeneity are two sides of the same coin” (Desmet, Ortuño-Ortín, & Wacziarg, 2015). However, it can be argued that although a nation is homogenous from an ERL perspective, there still may be diversity in values among the population in that country. In fact, when culture is defined narrowly as “those customary beliefs and values that ethnic, religious, and social groups transmit fairly unchanged from generation to generation” (Guiso, Sapienza, & Zingales, 2006, p. 23), we ignore the changes in the value-mix that takes place in society. In fact, Desmet et al. (2015) relying on the WVS data conclude that cultural heterogeneity and ethnolinguistic heterogeneity are uncorrelated. Venaik & Midgley (2015) also use the WVS and identify between four to six archetypes of values in China, India, the US and Japan. Thus, the value system of an individual or a society is not only influenced by ERL but is also affected by the changes in the general environment. Better access to knowledge, freer movement across geography, urbanization, religious reforms are some reasons that influences value systems as well. Thus, diversity within a nation can also be depicted through differences in values that individuals consider important irrespective of what the sources of those values are.

We argue that the positive effects of diversity on innovation reported by firm level studies cited earlier stems from values diversity rather than ERL diversity. In countries like Denmark and Holland where these studies were undertaken, ERL diversity is relatively low (Goren, 2013), and since the institutional framework allows for greater equality among the various groups, diversity could arise from differences in values orientation. Diversity in values orientation allows for a clash of opinions that encourages creativity. We propose that:

H2: *Values diversity contributes positively to innovation performance*

Despite claiming that ethnic diversity and cultural diversity explain two different variations in society, Desmet et al. (2015) do acknowledge that there is a degree of overlap between the two, and that it varies across geography. In other words, in some societies, differences in beliefs and reported attitudes can be easily identified by their ethnolinguistic background (e.g. South Asia, East Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa), while in other societies this link is fuzzy (e.g. Latin America). Thus, the combined effect of ERL diversity and values diversity needs to be explored. Based on H1 and H2, we would expect that:

H3: *High levels of ERL diversity and low levels of values diversity would be detrimental to innovation performance, and vice versa.*

3. Measuring ERL and values diversity

The measurement of ERL diversity is quite established in economics literature. Alesina et al. (2003), Alesina & Ferrara (2005), Montalvo & Reynal-Querol (2005), and Goren (2014) are among those who have refined its measurement.

Ethnic, religious or linguistic diversity is basically a Herfindahl based measure which takes on the following form:

$$1 - \sum_{i=1}^G p_i^2$$

Where p_i is the proportion of group i in the total population and G is the number of groups (ethnic, religious or linguistic) in that particular country. It represents the probability that two randomly selected individuals do not belong to the same group. Values range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating higher levels of diversity. The values of ethnic, religious and linguistic diversity for selected countries are shown in the Appendix. Briefly, African countries like Libya, Zambia and South Africa are among the most ethnically diverse countries while Asian countries like South Korea and Japan are among the least. This does not imply ethnic diversity is particularly continent specific as we do note that Indonesia is very diverse while Tunisia is not. In terms of religious diversity, South Africa, United States and Australia are very diverse while Yemen, Morocco and Turkey are less diverse. Finally, in terms of linguistic diversity, Zambia, South Africa and Mali are among the most diverse while South Korea and Yemen are least diverse. Thus, South Africa and South Korea seem to on either end of the spectrum of the ERL diversity.

As for values diversity, we introduce a new measure, one that is based on differences in values held by individuals within a nation. The measurement of cultural dimensions in the literature is dominated by three studies: Hofstede, Schwartz and the GLOBE project. Hofstede (1980, 2001) identified four main dimensions of culture: power distance, uncertainty avoidance, individualism and masculinity. Two more dimensions have been added since: long term orientation and indulgence versus restraint. Hofstede's measurement is well known in evaluating cultural distance between countries. Schwartz (1992) identified ten basic values recognized in cultures around the world. These ten values are then structured into four dimensions: Self-enhancement, Self-transcendence, Openness to change and Conservation; which are then explained in two orthogonal dimensions. The self-enhancement vs. self-transcendence dimension puts the pursuit of self-interest against the concern for welfare and the interest of others. Openness to change vs. conservation puts independent action and readiness for new experience on one end while self-restriction, order and resistance to change are on the other end. GLOBE is the most recent attempt at measuring cultural differences (House et al., 2004). It assessed nine dimensions of culture: assertiveness, institutional collectivism, in-group collectivism, future orientation, gender

egalitarianism, humane orientation, performance orientation, power distance and uncertainty avoidance. No doubt, there are similarities between some of the dimensions among all three studies, although some distinctness is also claimed (Lopez-Duarte & Vidal-Suarez, 2013).

We choose to use the Schwartz dimensions of culture simply because data is readily available at the individual level across 61 distinct countries through the World Values Survey database. The most recent two waves of the Survey (2005-2009 and 2010-2014) include ten statements relating to the ten basic values of Schwartz (1992, 1994). Data at the individual level is available for 50 countries in the 2008 wave and 20 countries in the 2012 wave, with 9 countries appearing in both waves.

We measure the degree of the heterogeneity in a population by estimating the probability that two randomly selected individuals that do not share the same set of beliefs and values will meet, similar to the ERL measure by Alesina et al. (2003) explained earlier. To do this, we first computed Schwartz's four value-constructs (self-enhancement, openness, self-transcendence and conservatism) from the ten value items provided by the WVS based on the method given by Lindeman & Verkasalo (2005). Then, for each country, we conducted cluster analysis to group individuals into clusters. We used the exploratory procedure of SPSS to explore the possible clustering solutions for each country. The procedure uses BIC or AIC to determine the number of cluster(s). The optimal number of clusters varied across countries, ranging between 3 and 7 clusters. We evaluated the quality of the 3-, 4-, 5-, 6- and 7-cluster solution for each country using the Silhouette coefficient. Clustering solutions with a Silhouette coefficient of 0.5 or above is indicative of highly separable clusters and considered acceptable (Mooi & Sarstedt, 2011). Using this criterion, only the 3-, 4-, 5- and 6-clustering solutions fulfilled the criteria mentioned above. For each cluster solution, we computed the probability that two randomly selected individuals that do NOT share the same set of beliefs and values will meet. We use the average of the four probabilities (one for each cluster solution) as an indicator of value diversity.¹

¹ We calculated the probability for each cluster solution. For example, the probability of a 3-cluster solution is computed from the sizes of three groups that exhibit high homogeneity within the group and high heterogeneity between groups, in terms Schwartz's four dimensions of human values. Let's say the size of each of the three clusters, W_1 , W_2 and W_3 , is given by u_1 , u_2 , and u_3 , respectively. $Pr(W_1 = k) = f(k; N, K, n)$ gives the probability that two randomly drawn individuals are from the same cluster when $k = n = 2$, $K = u_1$ and $N = u_1 + u_2 + u_3$. The complement of the sum of $Pr(W_1 = 2)$, $Pr(W_2 = 2)$ and $Pr(W_3 = 2)$ gives the probability that two randomly selected individuals are from different groups. A similar method was utilized by Montalvo & Reynal-Querol (2005) to measure ethnic heterogeneity. Since we have four feasible cluster solutions for each country, we have four probabilities. The average is used to measure value diversity. A high value of the measure is an indicative of high value diversity.

For instance, the United States scored a diversity value of 0.7408. This was computed as follows: First, we applied a cluster analysis to the 1184 US respondents of the WVS with respect to the four Schwartz's value constructs (Self-enhancement, Self-transcendence, Openness to change and Conservation). The 3-, 4-, 5-, 6-clustering solutions were all regarded as acceptable in quality with number of subjects in each cluster solution given by (555, 284, 345), (234, 384, 271, 295), (224, 344, 222, 289, 105), (135, 325, 133, 200, 286, 105), respectively. Members within the same cluster group share similar values. For the 3-clustering solution, the probability of getting two members with similar values i.e. from the same cluster is given by $M_3 = h(x = 2; N = 555 + 284 + 345, n = 2, k = 555) + h(x = 2; N = 555 + 284 + 345, n = 2, k = 284) + h(x = 2; N = 555 + 284 + 345, n = 2, k = 345) = 0.6384$ where $h(x; N, n, k) = \frac{[{}_k C_x][{}_N C_{n-x}]}{[{}_N C_n]}$. Using the

The higher the probability that two individuals with *different* value profiles will meet, the more diverse the society, as per the Alesina measure described earlier. Desmet et al. (2015) used a similar logic to measure cultural diversity although they included an average of 294 questions from the WVS to measure beliefs and attitudes. Since values are the underpinnings of these beliefs and attitudes (Schwartz & Rubel, 2005), relying on the battery of 10 Schwartz Values questions is deemed sufficient. In fact, the Pearson correlation test between our values diversity measure and the cultural diversity index by Desmet et al. (2015) is positively significant, providing an assurance that our values diversity measure is a robust measure.

The values diversity scores are shown in the Appendix 1. Sweden and Switzerland are among the most diverse countries in terms of the value mix while the most homogenous countries in our sample are Mexico and Algeria. Geography does not seem to explain values diversity, as countries that score higher are a mix bag of European, Asian and South American countries. On the other hand, the level of economic development may partly explain the degree of values diversity. The top five diverse countries (Sweden, Switzerland, Great Britain, Canada and South Korea) can be considered economically more developed while the bottom five (Mexico, Algeria, Ghana, Indonesia and Egypt) are middle income countries.

Table 1 below shows the correlation coefficients of the various types of diversity. Ethnic and linguistic diversities seem to be highly correlated. Values diversity is not significantly correlated with any of the other diversity indicators. This lends support to the findings of Desmet et al. (2015) who argued that diversity in beliefs and attitudes cannot be proxied by ethnicity.

TABLE 1. CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS OF VARIOUS DIVERSITY MEASURES
 (N=62, Sample included in the analysis)

DIVERSITY VARIABLE	ETHNIC	LINGUISTIC	RELIGIOUS	VALUES
Ethnic	1.000			
Linguistic	0.632**	1.000		
Religious	0.084	0.300*	1.000	
Values	-0.309*	-0.054	0.207	1.000

Note: ** and * denote 1% and 5% significance level, respectively.

4. Data, model and results

In addition to the four diversity measures explained above, two other variables completes our model, namely innovation output (the dependent variable) and innovation input (an independent variable). Both these variables are sourced from the most recent Global

same approach, the probability of getting two members with similar values from the same cluster for the 4-, 5- and 6-clustering solutions can also be calculated. The complements of this probability worked out to be 0.7419, 0.7419 and 0.8050, respectively. The average of the four resulting diversities is 0.7408.

Innovation Index (GII 2014 edition). The output sub-index is composed of 27 indicators across six areas of innovation activities including (1) knowledge creation, (2) knowledge impact, (3) knowledge diffusion, (4) intangible assets (e.g. trademarks and business models), (5) creative goods and services, and (6) online creativity¹. In this paper, we chose to use a single input variable, as the focus of our study is to evaluate the impact of the diversity variables.² The Input sub-index from the GII is composed of 54 indicators across five areas relating to the quality and quantity of innovation as well as the environment for innovation input including (1) institutional quality, (2) human capital and research, (3) infrastructure, (4) market sophistication, and (5) business sophistication. Thus our input variable include variables like R&D expenditure, proportion of the workforce with tertiary education, etc. Appendix 2 shows the various categories of data included in the GII.

Thus, we use a more comprehensive measure of innovation input and output than those used by previous studies.

4.1. Method 1: Partial Least Squares

Previous research on the national drivers of innovation has also alluded to the fact that culture plays a moderating role (Shane, 1995; Rauch et al., 2013) as opposed to a direct determinant (Shane, 1993; Taylor & Wilson, 2012; Efrat, 2014). Similarly, in the diversity-output growth literature, Alesina et al. (2003) and Montalvo & Reynal-Querol (2005) considered diversity as an independent variable while more recently, Goren (2014) evaluated ethnic diversity and polarization as moderating variables in their growth equations. In this study we test the causal relationships among the six variables using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique, in particular, the Partial Least Squares (PLS). PLS is a regression based technique that originates from path analysis. We select the method because it is a powerful tool for studying causal models with small sized sample (recommended minimum is 45) and its unique ability to estimate complex interactive and indirect relationships simultaneously. While traditional SEM modelling allows similar features but it requires us to impose strong distribution assumptions on samples (Tenenhaus, Vinzi, Chatelin, & Lauro, 2005; Chin & Newsted, 1999). Recent studies on innovation that employed PLS include Lai, Wang, & Chou (2009) and Chen & Guan (2011).

We consider a basic mediation model of path analysis in the form shown in Figure 1. If β_m is insignificant while β_d and β are significant, then innovation input is a complete mediation. If β_m is between 0 and the regression coefficient of the bivariate relationship between diversity and output, while β_d and β are significant, then innovation input is a partial mediation. If on the other hand, if β_m equals the regression coefficient of the bivariate relationship between diversity and output, then there is no mediation. We conducted the

¹ Given the various indicators used to measure these six components of innovation output, we can safely assume that what literature refers to as grassroots innovation is most likely not included in this index. Thus, whether cultural and/or values diversity has an effect on this type of innovation is beyond the scope of this paper.

² In previous research, various independent/control variables have been used including size of R&D expenditure, quality of education, Gross National Income (GNI), military expenditure, openness of the economy etc. (Efrat, 2014; Taylor & Wilson, 2012; Shane, 1993).

test of mediation using the four-step procedures described by Baron & Kenny (1986), Judd & Kenny (1981), and James & Brett (1984). The results are displayed in Figure 2.

FIGURE 1. BASIC DESCRIPTION OF PATH ANALYSIS

FIGURE 2a-d. RESULTS OF PATH ANALYSIS

Note: ***, ** and * represent 1%, 5% and 10% significance level.

In three of the four cases, β_m were not significantly different from zero whereas for all four cases β_d were significantly different from zero, suggesting that ethnic, religious and linguistic diversity has no direct effect on innovation output. However, these diversities are still important because their relationships to innovation input are still significant. This implies that ethnic, religious and linguistic diversities mediates the relationship between innovation input and output while linguistic diversity has a direct effect on output. These indirect effects how innovation is influenced by diversity through a causal sequence in which diversity influences the quality of input, which in turn influences output.

The estimates presented by Figure 2 establish the linkages between the four diversity variables, innovation input and output, we attempted to build a collective model that integrates all these links with additional interactions. Six possible interaction variables on

input from the product terms of the four diversity values were considered. The final fitted model¹ is schematically presented in Figure 3. Using the fitted model, we computed the **total effects** of each diversity indicator on innovation output, shown at the bottom of Figure 3.

4.2. Method 2: Systems Equation Model

While PLS offered a graphic interface for visualizing the relationships schematically with interpretations that are instinctive and intuitive, there are limited diagnostic statistics to evaluate the specifications of the model. Thus, to ensure more robust results, in addition to the path analysis, we also build a systems equation model to test our hypotheses. The modelling process includes fitting the equations listed in Table 2.

FIGURE 3. FINAL PATH MODEL

These equations can be described as follows:

- Equation (1) to examine the main effects of diversities on innovation input.
- Equation (2), (3) and (4) to examine the significance of interaction terms derived from Equation (1).
- Equation (5) to examine the main and interaction effects of diversities collectively.
- Equation (6) to examine the effects of the predicted innovation input on output.

¹ To reduce multi-collinearity, centered data was used. The output-input relationship was assumed to be a log-linear relationship. The estimation was done by using SmartPLS. Nonparametric bootstrap procedures were used to test the significance of estimated path coefficients. 5000 bootstrap samples were used.

We also checked the influence of the four diversity variables on innovation output when controlling for the effects of innovation input. i.e. $Output=f(Input, Ethnic, Religious, Linguistic, Value)$. The F-test for the fitted equation was 1.6626 ($p = 0.1606$), confirming that diversity has little direct effect on innovation output as found in the path analysis explained earlier.

Results of the fitted equations in Table 2 are reported in Table 3. From the fitted Equation (1), we find that only the coefficient for linguistic diversity, β_{14} , is insignificant, while all other coefficients are significant. The fitted Equation (2) to (5), which includes all main and interaction effects as R.H.S variables, show that the coefficients of (Value x Ethnic) and (Ethnic x Religion), together with their corresponding main effects, are significant determinants of innovation input.

TABLE 2. SYSTEMS EQUATION MODEL

$$\text{Eq (1): } Input = \alpha_1 + \beta_{11}Values + \beta_{12}Ethnic + \beta_{13}Religious + \beta_{14}Linguistic + e_1$$

$$\text{Eq (2): } Input = \alpha_2 + \beta_{21}Values + \beta_{22}Ethnic + \beta_{23}Religious + \beta_{24}(Values \times Ethnic) + e_2$$

$$\text{Eq (3): } Input = \alpha_3 + \beta_{31}Values + \beta_{32}Ethnic + \beta_{33}Religious + \beta_{34}(Values \times Religion) + e_3$$

$$\text{Eq (4): } Input = \alpha_4 + \beta_{41}Values + \beta_{42}Ethnic + \beta_{43}Religious + \beta_{44}(Ethnic \times Religious) + e_4$$

$$\text{Eq (5): } Input = \alpha_5 + \beta_{51}Values + \beta_{52}Ethnic + \beta_{53}Religious + \beta_{34}(Values \times Religious) + \beta_{34}(Values \times Religious) + \beta_{54}(Ethnic \times Religious) + e_5$$

$$\text{Eq (6): } Output = \alpha_6 + \beta_{61} \overline{Input} + e_6$$

$$\text{Where } \overline{Input} = [\alpha_5 + \beta_{51}Values + \beta_{52}Ethnic + \beta_{53}Religious + \beta_{34}(Values \times Religious) + \beta_{34}(Values \times Religious) + \beta_{54}(Ethnic \times Religious)]$$

In fact, Equations (5) and (6) form a simultaneous model that is useful for examining the effects of various diversities on innovation output through its effects on innovation input - a model that mirrors our previous path analysis. By design, innovation input in Equation (6) is endogenous, and so it is necessary to complete the estimations using an IV approach. The two equations can be fitted by the 2SLS method to preserve their linkages and to account for the correlated disturbances between equations. In fact, the two equations form a simultaneous equation system that is recursive and can be treated as a triangular case such that we can exclude some unnecessary instruments when applying the 2SLS method (Sanchez, 2005). Hence, we can use the predicted value from Equation (5) as the instrumented variable to estimate Equation (6)¹. We adjust the variance-covariance in order

¹ One may question the validity of including innovation input as the only driver of innovation output, while other variables like current and past R&D, stock patents, etc. should have been considered as valid candidates. As explained earlier, five categories of innovation input (see Appendix 2) have been embedded in the innovation input measure selected here.

to correct the standard error when applying the indirect least square method using procedures described in Gujarati (2003, 791).

TABLE 3. REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INNOVATION INPUT AND DIVERSITIES

EQUATION		CONSTANT	ETHNIC	RELIGIOUS	VALUES	LINGUISTIC	ETHNIC *RELIGIOUS	ETHNIC *VALUES	RELIGION *VALUE
1	Coefficient	46.186***	-20.367***	14.954**	314.416***	-6.598			
	Std. Error	1.261	5.865	6.418	86.190	5.264			
	t-Statistic	36.636	-3.473	2.330	3.648	-1.253			
	Prob.	0.000	0.001	0.023	0.001	0.215			
2	Coefficient	46.177***	-21.429***	12.251**	300.074***		-43.246		
	Std. Error	1.250	5.517	6.136	86.152		28.112		
	t-Statistic	36.945	-3.884	1.996	3.483		-1.538		
	Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.050	0.001		0.130		
3	Coefficient	46.247***	-21.295***	11.631*	324.981***			110.813	
	Std. Error	1.376	5.882	5.992	88.765			447.810	
	t-Statistic	33.605	-3.620	1.941	3.661			0.247	
	Prob.	0.000	0.001	0.057	0.001			0.805	
4	Coefficient	46.113***	-22.029***	10.654*	361.589***				-664.124*
	Std. Error	1.244	5.888	6.066	87.547				354.296
	t-Statistic	37.054	-3.741	1.756	4.130				-1.874
	Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.084	0.000				0.066
5	Coefficient	46.324***	-23.821***	12.518**	326.931***		-60.455**	503.108	-1172.740***
	Std. Error	1.265	4.905	6.046	82.215		27.538	450.359	413.950
	t-Statistic	36.626	-4.856	2.071	3.977		-2.195	1.117	-2.833
	Prob.	0.000	0.000	0.043	0.000		0.032	0.269	0.006
Specification	R ² =0.374, 0.385, 0.357, 0.377 and 0.434; Adjusted R ² =0.330, 0.342, 0.312, 0.333 and 0.372; RESET test=0.950, 0.141, 0.105, 0.156 and 1.1316								
Diagnos	Jarque Bera=0.434, 5.806, 4.286, 4.044 and 3.814; Max VIF=1.456, 1.678, 1.611, 1.443, 3.000 and 4.984;								
cs	White's Heteroskedasticity Test Statistic =14.779, 13.753, 14.179, 12.352 and 14.993								
for 1 to 5									
6	Output = 34.984 + 0.748Input ⁴ R ² =0.398, Adj.R ² =0.388, Jarque Bera=0.74, RESET=0.080, White's Heteroskedasticity Test Statistic =3.381								

To further address the concerns on the presence of omitted variable bias, a series of diagnostic tests have been carried out to ensure our models have the correct specifications. First, we checked the presence of simultaneity and/or omitted bias in Eq (5). Ramsey's RESET test was applied to test this specification bias. The relevant statistic is 0.1682 ($p = 0.6833$), i.e. fails by large margin to reject the null hypothesis of correct specification.¹ Second, the 2SLS approach is a suitable estimator for situations where the RHS variables are not exogenous. In our case, the endogeneity of the **Input** variable is given by design, since we ex-ante postulated that it is determined by diversity. We performed tests of overidentifying restrictions: Sargan $\chi^2 = 5.43764$ ($p = 0.1424$) and Basman $\chi^2 = 5.47971$ ($p = 0.1399$). These resulting statistics indicate that the residuals of Eq(6) is uncorrelated

¹ Indeed, the RESET statistics provides a test for three types of specification biases: not all important regressors were included, incorrect functional form and simultaneity.

with the selected instruments and thus the diversity variables pass the overidentification test. Similarly, the RESET test for Eq (6) is 2.055 ($p = 0.1575$), suggesting no evidence on the presence of omitted variable bias. The additional diagnostic statistics reported in Table 3 for each fitted equation, by and large, suggest that each fitted equation provides the required specification satisfactorily. Given the absence of specification bias, including additional control variables to both equations is redundant.¹

FIGURE 4a-d. INTERACTION EFFECTS AMONG DIVERSITIES ON INNOVATION

Figure 4a

Figure 4b

Figure 4c

Figure 4d

Now, for our results, the fitted Equation 5 shows that ethnic, religious and values diversities as well as their interactions can explain variations in innovation input. Turning to the interaction terms, the fitted equation 5 shows that (1) ethnic and religion, (2) value and religion are both significant. We include some visual aid (Figure 4) to assist the interpretation of these terms.

In Figure 4a, we observe that while ethnic diversity generally has a negative impact on innovation output, the adverse effect is stronger in countries with higher religious diversity. Similarly in Figure 4b, we find that religious diversity has an increased positive effect on innovation output when there is lower ethnic diversity. Figures 4c and 4d show that high

¹ Including additional controlling variables to Eq (5) require the newly included RHS variable to be uncorrelated with the error term of Eq (6). Most macro-variables would likely fail this particular requirement and thus we concluded that the current system of equations provides an optimal specification for the current study.

values diversity and low religious diversity combined are better for innovation. However, values diversity generally increases innovation output.

Results from both methods employed in this study are consistent. We have strong support for H1a and H2: Ethnic diversity has a negative impact on innovation performance, but values diversity has a positive effect. H1b and H1c have to be rejected since our results show that religious and linguistic diversities in fact have positive effects on innovation. The former influences innovation input, while the latter has a direct positive effect on innovation output. As for H3, there is some degree of support since our results points to the negative effect of (religious x values) diversity on innovation.

5. Discussion

The contribution of innovation to economic growth and development and the “hard” antecedents of innovation performance are well known (Freeman, 1990; Bartels et al., 2012). What is less known is the impact of socio-cultural forces on the patterns of technological innovation (Coccia, 2014). In this study we add to the literature on this lesser known area by evaluating the effects of various types of cultural diversities on innovation performance of a country. Although previous studies have considered such relationships, they are either at a firm level (Hunt et al., 2014) or at a sub-regional level (Niebuhr, 2006). Cross-country studies are scarce and focused on a particular type of diversity (e.g. religious diversity as in Coccia, 2014) or more generally link diversity and economic growth (Bove & Elia, 2017). Our results highlight five points vis-à-vis national innovation performance. First, cultural diversities tend to affect national innovation performance by influencing various inputs of innovation including R&D expenditure, education quality etc. In other words, it is more likely that cultural diversities (except linguistic diversities) have an indirect effect on innovation performance. This is consistent with studies like Halkos & Tzeremes (2013) which assumed that values and culture influences the way technological knowledge is distributed and created and Rauch et al. (2013) who modelled culture as a moderating variable affecting the innovation-growth relationship. Second, ethnic diversity has a negative influence on national innovation. Although a large number of firm level studies show ethnic diversity to have a positive influence on innovation performance, when considered at a country level, our results are more consistent with the negative impact of ethnic diversity on economic growth (Alesina & La Ferrara, 2005). This may imply that ethnic diversity decreases the quantity and/or quality of innovation input. At an extreme level, an ethnically diverse nation may allocate insufficient resources to the promotion of innovation because ensuring ethnic unity may be the priority. Third, unlike ethnicity, the diversity in values within society improves the effectiveness of innovation input. This implies that the diversity of opinions and synergy among team members that results in greater creativity and more efficient problem solving which previous research assumed came from ethnic diversity may in fact come from values diversity. Our results also imply that countries that are ethnically homogenous are able to promote innovation by promoting values diversity. However, we are unable to show that values diversity can overcome the negative influence of ethnic diversity as our interaction variable is insignificant in the model. Fourth, similar to Coccia (2014), our findings show that religious fractionalization has a positive effect on innovation. While the previous study tends to refer this positive effect exclusively to more

developed economies with more mature institutions, we add to this body of knowledge by showing that religious diversity specifically improves the effectiveness of innovation input. Although Benabou et al. (2015) find that religiosity is significantly associated with less favorable views of innovation, the diversity of religions within a society seems to indicate a more open and welcoming view of innovation. However, our findings also show that when religious and ethnic diversities interact, the latter overpowers the former, such that the final effect is negative. Finally, our results show the only direct effect of diversity on innovation output is linguistic fractionalization. Although the impact is marginally significant, it still shows the positive impact of multiple languages on innovation. It seems that linguistic diversity encourages the use of a common language to overcome communication challenges (Anderson & Paskericiute, 2006).

In one of the earliest study of culture and innovation, Shane (1993) concluded that individualism represented by autonomy, independence and freedom as well as greater risk tolerance makes some countries more innovative than others. Based on institutional theory, organizations are influenced by and reflect the values of the society that they are part of. Hence, such innovative qualities prevalent in a society are also present in organizations. Our results show that the diversity in such values is equally important. A society that comprises of individuals at different points in the values continuum, from self-enhancement to self-transcendence and from being open to being conservative, allows different mind-sets to co-exist within the same space. Such a society will be open to new ideas and accept differences, hallmarks to an innovative society. A team that is comprised of highly individualistic members may have many ideas but will suffer from implementation delays if ego dominates. In like manner, a team that has thinkers, planners and doers will be able to implement more innovative ideas. In a larger context, societies comprising of members with a diversified value profiles increase the efficiency of transforming innovation input into innovation output. Page (2007) explains, “... if people think alike, then no matter how smart they are, they most likely will get stuck at the same locally optimal solution. Finding new and better solutions, innovating, requires thinking differently. That’s why diversity powers innovation”. Our study has provided empirical evidence at the macro level to this statement.

Our findings have important implications to innovation policy. Countries that are planning to open their borders to cross-border migration should take note of the positive and negative effects of diversity on innovation performance. Inflow of migrants increases the ethnic diversity which can result in greater tensions if institutions like the rule of law and democracy are immature. This may reduce the effectiveness of innovation inputs. If, on the other hand, new migrants increase the values mix, this can have a positive impact on innovation inputs. Thus, careful selection of migrants based on values orientation is warranted. As stated by Lazear (1998:4) with regards to the United States, “... to obtain gains from diversity, it would be necessary to institute a selective immigration policy that eliminates relative-based preferences for immigrants and replaces them with a much more targeted approach”. Coupled with strong institutions, migration can add value to the economic development of a country. For developing countries, our findings points to the importance of creating a culture that is conducive for effective transformation of innovation input into meaningful output; a culture that appreciates various beliefs, attitudes and behavior. This can be achieved for instance by promoting an education system that allows

for independent thinking and a legal system that sets reasonable boundaries for the clash of opinions.

Further research that extends our study can take a few lines of enquiry. First, it would be useful to determine the specific innovation input that cultural diversities affect more. Identifying these inputs would allow policy makers to pay more/less attention on specific variables given the various diversities that exist within a society. Second, if values diversity is indeed a positive driver of innovation input, then identifying factors that promote values diversity is essential. Ashraf & Galor (2013a; 2013b) hypothesized that ethnic heterogeneity that exists across countries can be attributed to genetic diversity. This would mean that the negative effects of ethnic fractionalization on innovation can be considered permanent. However, our findings that values diversity positively moderates innovation input can be seen as a way out of this conundrum since previous studies suggest that, unlike ethnicity, values can change over time (Gurel-Atay et al., 2010; Li & Bond, 2010). While ethnic, religious and linguistic diversity is the result of cross border migration resulting from economic globalization, war and poverty, little is known about values diversity. To what extent do education systems, income inequalities and openness to trade for instance lead to greater values diversity? Answers to these questions could improve our understanding on the role of culture on innovation and economic growth.

6. Conclusion

In the current study, we developed a new measure of value diversity at the country level. Our analysis aimed to link value diversity to innovation. We conclude that not all types of diversity provide positive contributions to nation's innovativeness. While value and religious diversity can be regarded as significant input for innovation, ethnic diversity negatively correlates to innovation. Policymakers of ethnic diverse societies can use our empirical results, in conjunction with the framework on the *intercultural development continuum* described in Hammer (2012), to build a better environment where value diversity and individual differences among people are respected and appreciated.

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Appendix

APPENDIX 1. DIVERSITY VALUES

COUNTRY	VALUES	ETHNIC	LINGUISTIC	RELIGIOUS
Sweden	0.7591	0.0600	0.1968	0.2342
Switzerland	0.7587	0.5314	0.5441	0.6083
Great Britain	0.7570	0.1211	0.0532	0.6944
Canada	0.7564	0.7124	0.5772	0.6958
South Korea	0.7559	0.0020	0.0021	0.6604
Germany	0.7554	0.1682	0.1642	0.6571
Argentina	0.7547	0.2550	0.0618	0.2236
Hungary	0.7546	0.1522	0.0297	0.5244
Norway	0.7546	0.0586	0.0673	0.2048
Serbia & Montenegro	0.7541	0.5736		
Kuwait	0.7532	0.6604	0.3444	0.6745
Peru	0.7530	0.6566	0.3358	0.1988
Moldova	0.7523	0.5535	0.5533	0.5603
Australia	0.7521	0.0929	0.3349	0.8211
Malaysia	0.7521	0.5880	0.5970	0.6657
France	0.7520	0.1032	0.1221	0.4029
Morocco	0.7516	0.4841	0.4683	0.0035
China	0.7512	0.1538	0.1327	0.6643
Bahrain	0.7508	0.5021	0.4344	0.5528
Georgia	0.7507	0.4923	0.4749	0.6543
Taiwan	0.7507	0.2744	0.5028	0.6845
Zambia	0.7502	0.7808	0.8734	0.7359
Russia	0.7499	0.2452	0.2485	0.4398
Poland	0.7495	0.1183	0.0468	0.1712
Thailand	0.7480	0.6338	0.6344	0.0994
Chile	0.7473	0.1861	0.1871	0.3841
Netherlands	0.7464	0.1054	0.5143	0.7222
Spain	0.7458	0.4165	0.4132	0.4514
Uruguay	0.7457	0.2504	0.0817	0.3548
Yemen	0.7454		0.0080	0.0023
Turkey	0.7453	0.3200	0.2216	0.0049
Lebanon	0.7449	0.1314	0.1312	0.7886
Andorra	0.7440	0.7139	0.6848	0.2326
Mali	0.7438	0.6906	0.8388	0.1820
Slovenia	0.7428	0.2216	0.2201	0.2868
Cyprus	0.7424	0.0939	0.3962	0.3962
Colombia	0.7419	0.6014	0.0193	0.1478
Finland	0.7418	0.1315	0.1412	0.2531
Libya	0.7413	0.7920	0.0758	0.0570
South Africa	0.7409	0.7517	0.8652	0.8603
United States	0.7408	0.4901	0.5647	0.8241
Iran	0.7407	0.6684	0.7462	0.1152
Bulgaria	0.7405	0.4021	0.3031	0.5965
Singapore	0.7399	0.3857	0.3835	0.6561
Tunisia	0.7393	0.0394	0.0124	0.0104

APPENDIX 1. DIVERSITY VALUES

COUNTRY	VALUES	ETHNIC	LINGUISTIC	RELIGIOUS
Rwanda	0.7389	0.3238		0.5066
Trinidad and Tobago	0.7386	0.6475	0.1251	0.7936
Burkina Faso	0.7373	0.7377	0.7228	0.5798
Hong Kong	0.7370	0.0620	0.2128	0.4191
Brazil	0.7367	0.5408	0.0468	0.6054
Pakistan	0.7365	0.7098	0.7190	0.3848
Ethiopia	0.7360	0.7235	0.8073	0.6249
Ukraine	0.7319	0.4737	0.4741	0.6157
Iraq	0.7301	0.3689	0.3694	0.4844
Japan	0.7267	0.0119	0.0178	0.5406
India	0.7265	0.4182	0.8069	0.3260
Jordan	0.7256	0.5926	0.0396	0.0659
Romania	0.7256	0.3069	0.1723	0.2373
Viet Nam	0.7249	0.2383	0.2377	0.5080
Ecuador	0.7235	0.6550	0.1308	0.1417
Egypt	0.7231	0.1836	0.0237	0.1979
Indonesia	0.7193	0.7351	0.7680	0.2340
Ghana	0.7180	0.6733	0.6731	0.7987
Algeria	0.7052	0.3394	0.4427	0.0091
Mexico	0.7007	0.5418	0.1511	0.1796

Note: Ethnic, religious and linguistic diversities: Alesina et al., 2003. Values diversity - authors' own calculations.

APPENDIX 2. COMPOSITION OF INNOVATION INPUT AND OUTPUT USED IN THE GLOBAL INNOVATION INDEX (GII)

Source: The Global Innovation Index, <https://www.globalinnovationindex.org/about-gii>